

QUIZ

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following Latin expression means *it does not follow*?

- Non segue.
- Et non sequitur.
- Non sequitur.¹
- Non sequantur.

2. What is the difference between creative thinking and critical thinking according to the Coursepack studied in period one?

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*, 8th Edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 56.

- Creative thinking encourages to broaden ideas using brainstorming and mind mapping, while critical thinking encourages narrowing the focus or slope of ideas.²**
 - Creative thinking is used for literary writing and novels, while critical thinking encourages analysts to try new techniques like brainstorming to solve a problem.
 - Critical thinking is only used for problem solving and conclusions, while creative thinking helps discover new ideas for the research project.
 - Critical thinking is evaluating a topic that will help create the research question, while creative thinking focuses on considering new options without analysis or evaluation processes.
3. **According to Turabian style, what is the proper way of formatting parenthetical notes?**
- Formatting parenthetical notes need to have title, page, and author every time you use shortened parenthetical notes.
 - An academic essay should have supporting information, including hearsay evidence.
 - Insert a parenthetical note instead of a reference number at the end of a quotation, sentence, or clause. The note comes before rather than after any comma, period, or other punctuation marks when the reference is run into the text.³**
 - Parenthetical notes always include the author's name, but if you cite the work several times, you do not need to have the year or page; only if you mention the book once.
4. **Which of the following is the correct citation for a website?**

- Brooks, Susannah. 2011, “Long time Library.” The University of Wisconsin-Madison. News., September 1., Accessed on May 11, 2012, <https://universityof wisconsin.edu/news/1981>
- Brooks, Susannah., 2011 “*Long time Library.*” University of Wisconsin-Madison News, September 1. Accessed May 11, 2012. <https://universityofWisconsin.edu/news/1981>.
- Brooks, Susannah. 2011. “Long time Library.” University of Wisconsin-Madison News, September <https://universityof wisconsin.edu/news/1981>
- Brooks, Susannah. 2011 “Long time Library.” University of Wisconsin-Madison News, September 1, Accessed May 11, 2012. <https://universityof wisconsin.edu/news/1981>⁴**

5. **According to Bloomberg and Volpe, what is the function and purpose of the literature review?**

- It is a summative description of the notes and ideas organized to support the evidence related to the research question.
- The function of the literature review is to summarize different theories and arguments that would support the research question, aiming to serve as the common thread of the research
- The literature review provides a clear and balanced picture of leading concepts, theories, and data relevant to the research topic or subject of study. Serves to create new frameworks and perspectives on the issue generated.⁵**

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd Edition (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 2.

³ Kate L. Turabian, 99.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, 151.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Sage Publications, 2008), 46.

- The literature review is an organized list of references with summaries, abstracts, and notes that help the researcher throughout the analysis.
6. **When choosing a research approach while completing a qualitative dissertation, what should the researcher role be according to Bloomberg and Volpe?**
- Develops a rationale for integrating aspects for quantitative and qualitative research.
- Adopts an outsider point of view, attempting to remain unbiased, objective, and impartial.
- Examines topics, investigating relationships, and cause-effect phenomena.
- Adopts a flexible stance with an emic point of view acknowledging personal values, bringing own experience to bear on the study.⁶**
7. **What are the best practices for gender-neutral formulations according to the European Commission Style Guide? (select all that apply)**
- Using *he/she* instead of using the generic ‘he’ on documents.
- Use the plural as a generic form as it does not require a definite article.**
- For noun forms and certain occupations, refer to the commonly used firefighters, tradesperson, police officer, and craftsperson.**
- Use a second-person form or an imperative when translating manuals or sets of instructions, like ‘turn on your computer.’⁷**

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 15.

⁷ European Commission, *English Style Guide, A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2011), 47.

8. **Which of the following prefixes always require a hyphen?**
- Anti.
 - Pro.
 - Self.**⁸
 - Co.
9. **Which of the following IS NOT part of the steps involved in constructing a well-developed literary review?**
- Write a central idea for each topic sentence.**⁹
 - Identify and retrieve the literary review.
 - Review and analyze the literature.
 - Develop the conceptual framework.
10. **What are the elements the critical theory or advocacy paradigm refers to when conducting qualitative research?**
- Social action agenda, platform design, political debate.**¹⁰
 - Data collection of participants, liberal perspective, cultural values.
 - Social change, empowerment, context perspective.
 - Feminism, positivism, practical research.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, 46.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 51.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, 9.

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- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Sage Publications, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd Edition. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.